

DAMAGE MODELLING AND PROGNOSIS OF DELAMINATED COMPOSITE BEAM STRUCTURES IN BENDING.

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the findings of parametric finite element modelling studies into the effects of delamination damage on the stress and strain fields of composite cantilever beams in bending under uniform pressure loading. The characteristic damage effects are then utilised to propose a potential technique for composite structural prognosis.

Keywords: Composite Beams, Delamination Damage Modelling, Structural Prognosis, Strain Field Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

The effects of damage on composite structures need to be fully understood in order that the limitation on such structures in service can be better estimated. This has the potential to permit greater use of the composite performance envelope, allowing the design and maintenance of more efficient structures, through the implementation of structural health monitoring and prognosis. This paper presents the findings of parametric finite element studies into the effects of delamination damage. The case investigated here studies the effects of delamination on the stress and strain fields of composite cantilever beams in bending under uniform pressure loading. The use of strain field changes is shown to provide a potential solution for the identification, location and assessment of delamination damage in a non-destructive manner.

Many studies have been carried out into the causes and effects of delamination damage in composite structures. Specifically focusing on beam structures Majumdar and Suryanarayana [1] modelled a through-width delamination by subdividing a beam into two delamination regions (sub-laminates). Each of these sub-laminates was modelled as an Euler beam and the whole structure solved to satisfy global boundary conditions. Barbero and Reddy [2] used layer-wise linear approximation of the displacements through the thickness and Heaviside step functions to model local effects of delaminations in composite plates. Their model was used in a global-local analysis scheme wherein the local regions were modelled using the layer-wise theory and global regions were modelled using less refined theories.

Jiang and Shu [3] conducted studies of damage in composite laminates subjected to central and normal impact by 3-D finite element analysis. Their stress analysis was carried out by developing a constitutive equation of composite laminates coupled with the damage. They investigated the effects of the damage on the stress distribution in the laminates and used the stress distributions across the thickness of the non-damaged laminate to show the probable distribution of delamination. Caron, *et al*, [4] modelled the three-dimensional stress state in multi-layered composites using a laminate theory which considered the kinematics field per layer. The interlaminar stresses introduced represent the exact out-of-plane 3D stresses calculated at the interface between two layers.

To achieve structural prognosis Narayanan and Ramanujam [5] introduced an inverse analysis based method that requires less measurement efforts than those of conventional techniques. In this procedure strain fields are measured on a surface opposite to the damaged surface. Then general functions relating damage conditions to strain fields are established in order to identify structural damage.

This paper details the findings of FEM studies into the parametric effects of delamination damage on the strain fields of composite cantilever beams in bending. The potential to utilise strain field changes in order to identify delamination damage in composite structures is discussed, with a view to applying this approach to structural damage prognosis.

DELAMINATION MODELLING

The parametric effects of delamination damage in composite cantilever beams are detailed from the output of FEM (Finite Element modelling). The results presented are for the case of a quasi-isotropic composite laminate under uniform pressure loading along the top surface. The beam modelled has the dimensions 250 x 50 x 4mm and equivalent homogeneous orthotropic material properties representing an IM7-8552 carbon/epoxy composite.

The inclusion of a delamination in a FEM cantilever beam model causes changes in the structure's strain field, in the region of the delamination. These changes include a change in the strain gradient in the damage region and the creation of a pair of strain peaks in the damaged strain field as shown in Fig. 1 for analysis of a 2D beam structure. Strain changes occur throughout the thickness of a delaminated cantilever beam, above and below the delamination.

FEM has suggested that the size and location of delaminations in cantilever beams can be determined from the strain field peaks they produce. In the case of a single delamination the peak values of the change in strain locate the ends of a delamination and therefore this can be used to determine the delamination size and location Fig. 2. The strain gradient in the delamination region can be used to determine the depth at which a delamination may be located within a structure.

The change in strain field increases proportionally to delamination size. The delamination size does not affect the modified strain gradient, in the damaged region, as this is a function of delamination depth not size. Only the absolute peak strain values change provided all other variables remain constant. The magnitude of the strain field peak change increases linearly with delamination size, throughout the strain field. This trend is also true of the longitudinal location of a delamination, with the peak strain changes reducing linearly with the distance of the delamination from the cantilever root.

Fig. 1 - Plot of the x component strain distribution (ϵ_x) for a 2D beam analysis, with single 20mm centrally located delamination, in bending under uniform pressure loading.

The effect of delamination on a cantilever beam’s strain field is more complicated when the depth of the delamination is considered. This is because the strain field effects are only uniform throughout the thickness of the structure provided the delamination is located at the mid-plane. The closer a delamination is located to the mid-plane, the greater the magnitude of strain field changes throughout the structure. In the case of surface strain measurement, the closer the delamination is located to the mid-plane the greater the increase in strain field gradient, in the damage region. This surface strain gradient change is reduced linearly with delamination distance from the mid-plane. As the delamination location approaches the surface, the surface strain gradient change becomes negative as shown in Fig. 2. When delaminations are located in the shear dominated region of the strain field, near to the mid-plane, the $\Delta\epsilon_{max}$ throughout the beam thickness is directly proportional to the shear stress which can no longer be carried across the delamination.

If multiple delaminations of exactly the same size and longitudinal location are introduced, only one set of peaks are shown in the strain field, as the ends of each delamination are directly coincident. The magnitude of these strain peaks is related to a cumulative effect of

the combination of delamination sizes and depth locations. The change in strain gradient is related to the location of delaminations through the structure's thickness and their proximity to each other. Multiple delaminations cause greater strain gradient changes, in the damage region. Again this is related to the cumulative effect of the individual delaminations, provided the delaminations are equal in size and positioned at the same location.

Fig. 2 - Change in x component strain distribution ($\Delta\epsilon_x$) caused by a single 20mm centrally located delamination, in a 2D cantilever beam analysis under uniform pressure loading

The introduction of multiple delaminations of differing sizes and/or offset longitudinal locations creates a series of strain field peaks in the damaged region(s). Each end of each delamination is represented by a peak in the strain field. For the case detailed in Fig. 3 the top surface strain field is shown in Fig. 4. For this case, Fig. 3, the effect on the strain field is more complex than simply the superposition of the individual delamination effects. This is looked at in more detail later.

Fig. 3 - Diagram of 2D beam model containing 3 non-equal delaminations. (1) 25% depth 10mm (2) 50% depth 20mm (3) 75% depth 30mm. Beam size 250mm x 4mm.

In the case of a 3D cantilever model, with a single centrally located mid-plane delamination, FEM shows that there are two pairs of equal and opposite characteristic strain field changes caused by delamination damage. There is a strain gradient change within the

damage area (labelled 1 in Fig. 5) similar to that found in the 2D model, and also a strain gradient change just outside of the delamination region (labelled 2 in Fig. 5). This second pair of strain gradient changes is attributable to the 3D effects of anticlastic curvature as parts of the structure become unconstrained into the delamination region and re-constrained out of it.

Fig. 4 - Top surface strain field (ϵ_x) for a cantilever beam in bending containing three non equal delaminations evenly distributed through the beam thickness. (1) 25% depth 10mm (2) 50% depth 20mm (3) 75% depth 30mm. Beam size 250mm x 4mm.

Fig. 5 $-\Delta\epsilon_x$ field for surface of 3D beam structure in bending with a single 20mm full width delamination centrally located at the mid-plane.

This study has also shown that across the width of the strain field, for a damaged beam in bending, the $\Delta\varepsilon_{x_{\max}}$ value changes. This change in the peak value does not follow a consistent pattern and is dependent on the width of delamination in relation to the beam width. In small delaminations (<50% beam width) the $\Delta\varepsilon_x$ increases from edge to centre line, as shown in Fig. 6, with this trend being reversed for larger delamination widths, as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6 - $\Delta\varepsilon_x$ field for surface of 3D beam structure in bending with a single 20 x 20mm delamination centrally located at the mid-plane.

Fig 7 - $\Delta\varepsilon_x$ field for surface of 3D beam structure in bending with a single 40 x 40mm delamination centrally located at the mid-plane

These effects are again due to the anticlastic bending effects of the structure separating into two parts in the delamination region. Hence the opposite effect is also seen as the structure is re-constrained together outside of the damage area.

POTENTIAL FOR DAMAGE PROGNOSIS

In order to utilise this knowledge of delamination effects on structural strain fields to create a prognosis system for estimation of useful remaining life or structural integrity, the process presented above needs to be reversed. Rather than determining strain fields effects from delaminations inputs, the delamination sizes and locations would need to be output from strain field measurement data.

In order to achieve this, the first step is to find the constituent strain field components which can be used to build up damage strain fields and understand the information that can be gained from this. In the simple cases of a single delamination or multiple delaminations of equal size and location, measurement of strain field peaks and gradient change could be sufficient to directly locate and size delaminations. The linear patterns of strain field change make these cases simple to deduce.

Earlier it has been explained that the output strain field of a structure with multiple delaminations of different size and/or location are more complex. Take for example the case presented in Fig. 3. An initial estimate of this strain field can be made by simply the superposition of the individual effect of each delamination on the structure's strain field. The result of such an output is shown in Fig. 8.

As it can be seen from Fig. 8, although most of the major characteristics of the strain damaged strain field are detailed at the surface, there is a large room from improvement especially in the internal region of the structure's strain field. This suggests that there are more characteristic strain field changes caused by the interactions of delaminations.

Fig. 8 – Strain field (ϵ_x) at five locations through the thickness of a 2D cantilever beam in bending containing three non equal delaminations and comparison of linear superposition estimate.

In order to improve the estimate of the strain field, in the damage region of this case, further strain field characteristics need to be added to the simple linear superposition of the

individual delaminations. In this case of a 2D model, the delaminations are modelled through the entire width of the structure. Each delamination therefore splits the beam into parts above and below it, effectively creating two small beams constrained together outside of the delamination region. The strain field trends found with single delaminations can be explained by superimposing the strain fields of the damage region small beam parts into the larger strain field of the structure. Take for example a beam with a single mid-plane delamination. The damage strain field of this example can be constructed by superimposing the strain field of an undamaged beam, of half the thickness, into the original undamaged beam's strain field, above and below the mid-plane in the damage region. Effectively this is simply considering the structure to be two separate beams in the delamination region.

If a similar principle is applied to the estimation of the multiple delamination strain field in Fig. 3 then further characteristics can be added. Fig. 9 is a diagram representing each of the component strain fields of this estimation. The central delamination (labelled 2 in Fig. 3) creates two extra strain field components (labelled A and E in Fig. 9). These are the top part and bottom part of the beam created by Delamination 2, and these strain fields are added to the three individual delamination strain field components used in Fig. 7 to produce the improved strain field estimation shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 9 – Diagram of the 5 single delamination components combined to generate the damaged strain field approximation for a beam section with 3 non-equal length delaminations distributed through the thickness as shown in Fig 3.

The components A and E from Fig. 9 are the extra delamination components added to the linear superposition estimation. These are half thickness beam section models to represent

the beam parts created by Delamination 2 at the mid-plane. It should be noted that components A and E from Fig. 9 are only half the beam thickness because Delamination 2 is located at the mid-plane and hence creates 2 equal half beam parts. If Delamination 2 were to be moved away from the mid-plane, A and E would no longer be equal in thickness.

The superposition technique demonstrated here (Fig. 10) shows that it is possible to build up a good estimate of the strain field for a multiple delaminated structure from the individual component delaminations and beam parts created by delaminations. If the opposite idea were considered and we were to take the strain change, caused by multiple delaminations in a structure, and break it down into the defining characteristics of each individual delamination, then we would have the first step to Structural Prognosis. It would potentially be possible to identify, quantify and locate each individual delamination in a structure from the strain field change at the surface or indeed at any location through a structures thickness provided that the location of the sensors in the strain field is known.

Fig. 10 - Strain field (ϵ_x) at five locations through the thickness for a cantilever beam in bending containing three non equal delaminations and comparison of enhanced linear superposition estimate.

CONCLUSIONS

Strain field measurements could be used to non-destructively identify and quantify delamination damage, provided sensors with sufficient resolution to identify the strain field changes are used. Potentially either surface measurement or output from embedded sensors could be utilised to determine delamination damage, provided the location of the sensor is known.

Characteristic delamination damage patterns have been described and their effect throughout the stress and strain field of a beam in bending explained. The effects of

delamination on a strain field, for a beam in bending, are shown to be due to the superposition, of the strain fields of each beam section created by delaminations, into the larger strain field of a structure.

The strain field effects in the case of a 3D structure have been detailed and shown to cause a change in the strain field across a beams width. This has been attributed to the anticlastic bending of the beam parts created by delamination damaged acting independently.

Structural Prognosis of this nature, utilising strain field data, would be reliant on 4 major steps:

- Identifying all pairs of the strain field change peaks. This would be critical as the first step as this information would dictate the eventual accuracy of any system.
- Using identified strain field change peaks to determine the number, size and longitudinal location of delaminations. This could be relatively straight forward as each pair of peaks identifies the start and end of an associated delamination.
- Identifying strain field gradient changes in the damage region.
- Using strain field gradient changes to determine the depth location of each delamination.

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